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Prospects of two-line hybrid rice breeding in Tamil Nadu, India

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Chill temperature from panicle initiation to heading is necessary for temperature-sensitive genic male-sterile (TGMS) lines for their self seed set through pollen fertility. Hence, an ideal location or season with favorable temperature is required for breeding new TGMS lines and their own seed multiplication. Tamil Nadu State (TN) in India has high elevation suitable for using the TGMS system to develop two-line hybrid rice. Annually, 2.2 million ha of rice are cultivated in TN, of which 1,000 ha are raised in valleys on the hills under cool climate.

Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU) initiated studies in 1995 to develop a TGMS system for the hills and plains of TN. The TGMS source materials available at TNAU were screened during rice-growing seasons for pollen sterility at three research stations at Coimbatore, Trichy, and Thirupathisaram in TN. One new research station was started at Gudalur town on the hill of Nilgiris at an altitude of 1200 m. Single plants possessing complete pollen sterility at all research stations were selected, transported, and ratooned at the hill station at Gudalur under cool temperatures to induce pollen fertility. Such selection was continued repeatedly under a fertility- and sterility-inducing environment until homozygosity was attained. The presence of more exerted stigma was the key criterion in choosing prospective TGMS single plants for advance-

ment. Critical temperature-inducing pollen fertility or sterility in the field was estimated, taking into consideration the corresponding maximum, minimum, and average temperature during 30 d before heading. From the initial evaluation and selection, one very early TGMS line, TS29, was evolved during 1998 and 15 more prospective TGMS lines were selected during 2001 (Table 1).

Table 1. Duration and stigma exertion of prospective TGMS lines at Thirupathisaram, TN.

TGMS line	Duration (d)	Stigma exertion (%)
TS29	100	50
GD98013	125	42
GD98014	123	38
GD98029	125	63
GD98049	122	61
GD98091	128	52
GD98168	114	63
GD98179	119	57
GD99004	125	42
GD99007	155	40
GD99009	117	65
GD99017	117	61
GD99018	123	54
GD99036	127	59
GD99042	128	63
GD99049	125	66
GD99051	125	61

Pollen fertility and seed multiplication studies were carried out on hills with TS29. Pollen fertility was more than 60% from June to January. But seed set was high only up to the first fortnight of December (see figure). When minimum temperature dropped below 15 °C (from December to February), seed set decreased. Maximum temperature exceeding 29 °C during March and April induced pollen sterility (Table 2). The range of average temperature that caused high seed set in the TGMS line was 19–21 °C; the maximum temperature ranged from 21 to 26 °C and the minimum from 15 to 18 °C. This ideal temperature regime extended from June to November at Gudalur.

The rice valleys occupying 800 ha around Gudalur on the Nilgiris Hill can be used for seed multiplication of the TGMS line. Proper time of sowing and harvest ensures a seed yield of 3 t ha⁻¹. Plenty of rainfall and favorable temperature are the key factors during this season. Sowing may be undertaken in June for TGMS lines with medium duration and

Percent of pollen fertility and seed set of TGMS lines at Gudalur, 1997-99.

in July for lines with short duration to have the harvest in November-December. Rice valleys are surrounded on the slope by tea and coffee gardens that serve as natural pollen barriers. Because of low temperature, the growth duration of the TGMS line was extended by 25 d in the hills compared with that in the plains.

The pollen sterility studies with TS29 at Gudalur and at the research stations in the plains revealed that the sterility-inducing average temperature is 24 °C. It is also important that the maximum temperature does not fall below 29 °C during the critical stage. In the TN plains, the temperature prevailing for 9 mo, from February to October, is favorable in inducing complete pollen sterility. In the rice-growing areas of TN, the maximum temperature during this period ranges from 30 to 37 °C, with a minimum of 23–26 °C. This situation ensures safe hybrid seed production in the plains. However, during winter (Nov-Jan), the average temperature falls below 24 °C. A maximum temperature below 29 °C induces partial pollen fertility in TGMS lines. This situation also occurs

Table 2. Monthly rainfall and temperature at Gudalur, 1996-99.

Month	Rainfall (mm)	Temperature (°C)		
		Maximum	Minimum	Mean
January	6	26	10	18
February	3	29	12	21
March	9	30	13	22
April	69	29	16	23
May	130	28	17	22
June	457	24	17	21
July	684	22	16	19
August	388	23	17	20
September	255	24	16	20
October	201	25	16	21
November	84	25	15	20
December	30	25	13	19

Table 3. Grain yield of two-line hybrids in multilocation trials in TN, 2000-01.

Two-line hybrid	Mean of nine locations		Percent yield increase
	Duration (d)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
TS29/ASD16	112	5.1	5.5
TS29/ASD18	108	5.0	2.8
TS29/MDU5	107	5.2	6.5
TS29/ADT43	110	4.8	-1.6
TS29/TRYR2	112	4.7	-2.9
ADT43 (check)	114	4.9	0

during June-August in the high-rainfall zone in TN. Detailed studies are needed on the stability of TGMS lines during this period.

Two-line hybrid seed production was carried out for five hybrid combinations, using TS29 as the female parent, at the agricultural colleges and research stations situated at Killikulam, Madurai, Aduthurai, and Trichy in

TN. These hybrids were evaluated in multilocation trials during 2000-01 at nine locations. The maximum yield increase was only 6.5% over the check ADT43 because of the poor combining ability of TS29 (Table 3). The improved TGMS lines are now used for seed production to develop better hybrids.

Single recessive genetic female sterility in rice

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In September 1999, we found a completely sterile mutant plant (Yeungnam University, Acc. No. G39) in a farmer's field in Korea. In late spring 2000, the plant stock of G39 was ratooned in the

greenhouse and then test-crossed with several varieties, including male-sterile lines (Dian-type CMS lines) and male-sterile restorer lines. No seed set at all was observed in crosses when the sterile

plant G39 was used as a maternal parent. In contrast, the spikelets of the sterile plant G39 flowered normally and shed pollen grains, which, when pollinated to Dian-type japonica CMS lines or